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variance for all the traits (except kernel length after cooking and linear elongation ratio) indicated the predominance of additive gene action (Table 1).

IR50 possessed desirable GCA effects for kernel length, kernel breadth, kernel

thickness, L-B ratio, kernel length after cooking, kernel breadth after cooking, and linear elongation ratio. IR50 was found to be the best parent because of its desirable GCA effects for five traits (Table 2). ADT39 was the next best

parent. IR50 and ADT39 could be used in hybridization programs for improving grain quality traits through recombination breeding and for getting desirable segregants. ■

Breeding methods

Heterosis for kernel characters in rice

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Information is limited on the extent of heterosis for kernel characters in rice. We studied the heterotic manifestations of four kernel characters in 15 hybrids involving eight parents.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications during 1991-92 wet season (Oct-Feb) at TNRRI. Each genotype (parents and hybrids) was planted in two 3-m rows at 30- × 20-cm spacing. Observations were recorded for 10 randomly selected plants per replication.

Seeds were hulled in a McGill sample sheller. Kernel length and L-B ratio were measured with a Mitutoyo micrometer. Grain was milled in a Kett rice polisher and cooked by the method of Juliano and Perez. Kernel elongation was computed as the ratio of mean length of cooked rice to that of milled rice. The performance of hybrids over mid-parent (di) and better parent (dii) was estimated following standard procedures.

Heterosis for kernel length was low. Improved White Ponni/ADT41 and IR50/Kasturi expressed significant and positive relative heterosis. Heterosis for kernel L-B ratio was significant and negative, indicating that none of the hybrids were superior for grain fineness. Relative heterosis for kernel length after cooking was positive and significant in five crosses. Heterosis over mid-parent and better parent for kernel elongation was positive and highly significant in six hybrids (see table).

Relative heterosis (di) and heterobeltiosis (dii) in % for kernel characters in selected crosses.^a TNRRI, Aduthurai, India. 1991-92 wet season.

Cross	Kernel length		Kernel L:B ratio		Kernel length after cooking		Kernel elongation	
	di	dii	di	dii	di	dii	di	dii
ADT37/ADT41	-3.1**	-22.1**	-11.4**	-36.9**	2.7*	-16.6**	9.2**	5.2**
ADT39/ADT41	-1.9**	-17.2**	-6.8**	-26.0**	1.4	-14.2**	4.0**	3.3*
ADT39/Kasturi	-2.6**	-16.0**	-11.5**	-29.3**	2.8*	-11.2**	8.8**	8.8**
IR50/Kasturi	0.7*	-5.6**	-5.1**	-15.6**	12.5**	-4.4**	12.2**	11.5**
Improved White Ponni/ADT41	1.9**	-14.7**	-4.1**	-21.5**	13.2**	-3.6**	11.9**	11.9**
Improved White Ponni/Kasturi	-1.2**	-15.5**	-9.2**	-25.2**	3.6*	-9.9**	8.0**	7.3**

*, ** = significant at 1 and 5% level, respectively.

IR50/Kasturi and Improved White Ponni/ADT41 show promise for improving kernel length, kernel length after cooking, and kernel elongation through heterosis breeding. ■

High-yielding somaclonal variants of Basmati 370

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Improving basmati varieties through cross breeding results in recombination of various genes for yield and quality. But

these new combinations often do not yield the desired basmati quality. We have been researching ways to accelerate the improvement of both quality and yield of basmati rices.

We obtained a series of somaclonal variants with desired characteristics. Seeds of Basmati 370 were inoculated on MS medium with 2 mg 2,4-D/liter. Calli were subcultured 12 times on the same

Table 1. Agronomic performance of somaclonal variants.^a NARC, Islamabad, Pakistan.

Variant	Flowering (d)		Plant height (cm)		Tillers/hill (no.)		1,000-grain weight (g)		Fertility (%)	Yield (t/ha)
TF4	114	de	120	f	12	e	17.33	cd	89.0	a
SN85	127	b	140	c	14	cd	16.00	de	65.0	de
SN1-80	129	ab	147	b	14	cd	14.33	e	65.0	de
TF11	115	de	116	g	15	bc	13.67	e	63.3	de
SN12	116	cd	113	h	13	de	19.00	abc	70.0	c
TF8	113	e	123	e	13	de	17.67	bcd	65.0	de
TF9	116	cd	127	d	20	a	17.33	cd	66.3	cd
TF10	118	c	123	e	16	b	16.00	de	61.7	e
Basmati 385	114	de	122	e	15	bc	21.00	a	80.0	b
Basmati 370	130	a	150	a	9	f	20.00	ab	70.0	c
LSD (5%)	2.142		2.187		1.265		2.38		3.514	0.5868
CV (%)	1.05		0.99		5.23		8.08		2.95	9.90

^aMeans in a column followed by the same letter are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT.

Table 2. Grain quality characteristics of TF4 and Basmati 370. NARC, Islamabad, Pakistan.

Genotype	Head rice (%)	Kernel			Quality index L:B×T	Kernel		
		Length (mm)	Breadth (mm)	Thickness (mm)		Size	Shape	Type
TF4	55.4	6.9	1.73	1.55	2.6	Long	Slender	Fine
Basmati 370	55.6	6.7	1.70	1.60	2.5	Long	Slender	Fine

MS medium, with a 15-d interval between subcultures. Three hundred 3-mm calli were transferred to LS medium for regeneration.

Plants regenerated were termed R0 plants. Seeds collected from these plants

were the source of R1 plants, and R2 plants were raised from seed collected from R1 plants. About 60% of the lines differed from the parental variety. Eight R2 lines (TF4, TF8, TF9, TF10, TF11, SN12, SN85, and SN1-80) were early

flowering, stiff stemmed, short, and had acceptable grain appearance. They were evaluated in the field for agronomic performance. Results indicated that plant height and days to flowering were reduced significantly compared with those of Basmati 370. TF4 was the most promising variant (Table 1). This line had comparatively greater grain length than Basmati 370 (Table 2). TF8, TF9, and SN12 yielded at par with Basmati 370. Somaclonal variants produced through tissue culture may be used as additional sources of interesting variability for rice breeding. ■

Effect of regeneration media on shoot production from anther cultures of rice

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To identify a medium that could be used on crosses between a wide variety of rice (*Oryza sativa*) cultivars, we investigated the ability of four regeneration media to induce shoots from anther-derived calli. Panicles were selected from F₁ plants of 11 crosses of cultivars and breeding lines at the Texas A&M/USDA Agricultural Research and Extension Center, Beaumont, Texas, USA. Parents included the US long-grained javanica rice cultivars Cypress, Jodon, L202, Lemont, and Toro-2 and the Chinese indica cultivar Teqing. Three unreleased US breeding lines were also used, including javanica line 90102065, indica line MB231, and MB302, derived from an indica × japonica cross.

Panicles containing microspores at the early- to mid-uninucleate stage were collected from field-grown plants and were kept at 6-8 °C in the dark for 3-4 d. They were sterilized with 40% bleach for 16 min, followed by three sterile water washes. Anthers were then removed from the florets, placed on callus induction medium, and incubated

Plants produced from 11 crosses on 4 regeneration media.

Cross ^a	Total (no.)	(%) ^b	N6NB		MSNBC		MSMU		MSCIB	
			no.	%	no.	%	no.	%	no.	%
CPRS/MB231										
Anthers	5730									
Calli	543	9.5	138		200		148		57	
Shoots	15	2.8	0	0	4	2.0	11	7.4	0	0
CPRS/Toro-2										
Anthers	5600									
Calli	727	13.0	203		274		166		84	
Shoots	20	2.8	5	2.5	9	3.3	6	3.6	0	0
Jodon/Toro-2										
Anthers	6685									
Calli	1506	22.5	547		503		310		146	
Shoots	9	0.6	0	0	0	0	7	2.3	2	1.4
L202/MB231										
Anthers	3360									
Calli	275	8.2	40		102		75		60	
Shoots	14	5.1	0	0	10	9.8	3	4.0	1	1.7
L202/TQNG										
Anthers	5535									
Calli	668	12.1	212		254		137		65	
Shoots	4	0.6	0	0	1	0.4	3	2.2	0	0
L202/Toro-2										
Anthers	8230									
Calli	2345	28.9	821		819		377		328	
Shoots	20	0.9	4	0.5	12	1.5	2	0.5	2	0.6
LMNT/Toro-2										
Anthers	7430									
Calli	2021	27.2	785		732		315		189	
Shoots	15	0.7	0	0	8	1.1	5	1.6	2	1.1
TQNG/MB231										
Anthers	10,815									
Calli	600	5.6	213		184		138		65	
Shoots	58	9.7	9	4.2	23	12.5	20	14.5	6	9.2
TQNG/Toro-2										
Anthers	6950									
Calli	1937	27.9	486		777		504		170	
Shoots	60	3.1	3	0.6	32	4.1	20	4.0	5	2.9
2065/MB231										
Anthers	2750									
Calli	197	7.2	-		115		82		-	
Shoots	10	5.1	-		4	3.5	6	7.3	-	
2065/MB302										
Anthers	5125									
Calli	205	4.0	-		94		111		-	
Shoots	16	7.8	-		2	2.1	14	12.7	-	
All crosses										
Anthers	68,210									
Calli	10,960	16.1	3445		4023		2328		1164	
Shoots	221	2.0	21	0.6	92	2.3	90	3.9	189	1.5

^aCPRS = Cypress, TQNG = Teqing, LMNT = Lemont. ^bCalculated as percentage of anthers forming calli and percentage of calli forming shoots.